

PID-optimised workflows:

A vision of a more efficient future

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Introduction

This report accompanies four expansive diagrams, each of which is intended to showcase a possible future, in which persistent identifiers (PIDs) are used throughout the research lifecycle to enable automation, efficiency, new discovery tools, and analysis. The use of open PIDs throughout also supports greater transparency and reproducibility in research activities and communications.

Anyone can use these diagrams and adapt them to meet their own workflows. This is, after all, just one vision of a PID-optimised future, and one that is by necessity somewhat generic. The goal is to inspire all those working to support research and innovation to consider how they could use powerful, global, open research information infrastructures in new ways to improve the health and resilience of the ecosystem.

This work emerged from a programme of activities commissioned by Jisc in the UK and sponsored by Research England. It was carried out by the MoreBrains Cooperative, and included the development of a national PID roadmap for the UK, with the goal of supporting a strong research base and enabling a smoother transition to more openness at every step, from applying for a grant to communicating research findings.

At the start of the programme, five 'priority PIDs' were selected, based on a series of workshops and community discussions¹. Given the nature of PIDs as both coordinates and signposts in the information landscape, the use of open PID systems was seen as essential. The consensus list of entities for which PIDs would provide the greatest benefits was therefore matched to relevant open PID systems, all of which have some form of community governance.

The following priority PIDs were selected:

1. Crossref² Digital Object Identifiers³ (DOIs) for funding grants of all kinds
2. Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier⁴ (ORCID) IDs for people
3. Research Activity Identifiers⁵ (RAIDs) for projects
4. Research Organization Registry⁶ (ROR) identifiers for organisations
5. Crossref and DataCite⁷ DOIs for outputs (especially articles and data)

Community discussions⁸ and a survey⁹ in 2020 helped to refine the expectations for these PIDs, and provided an additional set of priorities: the workflows in which the community felt increased use of PIDs would have the greatest impact. These are:

1. Funding awards, from application to reporting and evaluation

¹ Brown, Josh (2020) Developing a persistent identifier roadmap for open access to UK research. <https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/7840/>

² <https://www.crossref.org/>

³ <https://www.doi.org/>

⁴ <https://orcid.org/>

⁵ <https://www.raid.org.au/>

⁶ <https://ror.org/>

⁷ <https://datacite.org/>

⁸ Murphy, Fiona and Jones, Phil (2020) Jisc PID Agency: Focus Group Report. <https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/8166/>

⁹ Brown, Josh and Meadows, Alice (2020) Persistent identifiers adoption and awareness survey report. <https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/8107/>

2. Institutional research management
3. Research article publication
4. Research data management and publication

Further research by MoreBrains into the benefits PIDs could bring to these workflows served to underscore the need for a clear pathway to optimal use of PIDs in research systems, services, and toolkits¹⁰. It also emphasised the fact that much of the power of PIDs comes not from their ability to uniquely and permanently identify a 'thing', but from the descriptive information (metadata) that accompanies each PID, the associations between PIDs, and the discovery and other tools that are offered by the organisations that provide PIDs, or by their partners.

Armed with all this information, the MoreBrains team conducted a global consultation on how a 'PID-optimised' version of the priority workflows could operate. We then endeavoured to distil the complex and diverse real-world processes uncovered during the consultation, into PID-focused, generic representations. Our goal was not to capture every step, but instead to present a version of the future in which most participants in the research lifecycle will recognise enough of their own professional activities to be able map the workflows onto their own activities, and to start envisaging a pathway towards a PID-optimised future.

In this report we suggest some initial steps that key stakeholder groups could take now that would lay foundations for the vision set out in the diagrams. We work backwards from our ideal-world version to the reality on the ground now, and identify the benefits that could accrue even from just these first steps on the journey to a more efficient, transparent, and open research ecosystem.

The development of the workflows

The workflow diagrams are based on two major inputs: a view of current common practices and an analysis of the potential of current PID systems. The common practice components were derived from workshops with expert practitioners and then mapped onto a linear structure. We focused on aspects of the practice that would be most amenable to PID-optimisation, so the workflows do not include every imaginable step.

It is also important to note that the linear approach makes for an easier-to-read diagram, but can hide the fact that some aspects of the workflow will occur in different sequences, or be cyclical, and in some cases may not apply in every discipline, context, or circumstance. Research practice is always evolving, and our goal was to produce a representation of the workflows in which most readers would recognise at least some of the steps we identified.

One example of this is that a project may be associated with one grant, several grants, or no grants at all. In the latter case, readers may simply choose to skip the steps that refer to linking outputs to grants, although we note that the principles at work may be useful for recording other kinds of relationships between project participants, outputs etc. and other administrative entities.

The UK's priority PIDs, which were heavily influenced by the early project focus on the ongoing transition to more open research, are emphasised throughout the workflows. The potential of these

¹⁰ Brown, Josh, Jones, Phill, Meadows, Alice, Murphy, Fiona, & Clayton, Paul. (2021). UK PID Consortium: Cost-Benefit Analysis (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4772627>

PIDs to support other policy agendas, such as FAIR data or reducing bureaucratic burden, has become obvious as the project went on. In other contexts, such as for specific disciplines, or for alternative policy frameworks, other PIDs may be a higher priority than the five used here. The workflows can therefore be remixed or extended to add other PIDs that are a higher priority for your community.

Our hope is that anyone involved in working in research will be able to find an example of how comprehensively-adopted PIDs could improve their working life by either reducing burden and/or enabling things that are currently not possible or too labour-intensive to be normal practice.

Prioritisation

As part of the programme of activities that led to this report, the 2020 survey¹¹ clearly indicated that funding, institutional research management, and content publication were the highest priority for analysis. After several rounds of discussion with the project stakeholder group and the UK's Research Identifier National Coordinating Committee (RINCC)¹², 'content publication' was split into two separate workflow diagrams. One focuses on journal articles, with pathways that include both preprints and green open access via repository deposit of an Author's Accepted Manuscript (AAM); the second looks specifically at research data.

Consultation

For each workflow, a community workshop was organised (a full list of participants can be found in the acknowledgements at the end of this report). Some individuals attended more than one workshop, and/or contributed to more than one workflow. Insights from subsequent workshops (such as the vital importance of capturing PIDs and metadata at the earliest possible stage) were used to inform the editing and refinement of all the workflows.

Workshops were conducted virtually, led by members of the MoreBrains team and using the Miro¹³ online whiteboard app to capture ideas, comments, use cases, and issues. A matrix was used to structure input, with each horizontal row representing one stage in the relevant life cycle (for instance applying for a grant, reviewing a grant application, awarding a grant, and so on). We worked along each row, gathering input on which stages were critical to the group and highlighting areas where participants felt PIDs could be used better, or introduced to improve the processes.

Design

Once again, Miro was used to develop the draft workflows, which used a tried and tested model, developed in 2017 and 2018, to showcase how multiple identifiers could be used across the publication process to create efficiencies¹⁴. In this model, the diagram is broken into four columns:

¹¹ Brown, Josh and Meadows, Alice (2020) Persistent identifiers adoption and awareness survey report. <https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/8107/>

¹² <https://rincc.org.uk/>

¹³ <https://miro.com/>

¹⁴ Brown, Christopher, Brown, Josh, Jacobs, Neil, Meadows, Alice, and Tatum, Clifford (2018) Mapping the PID Landscape. Blog post, published by ORCID. Available at: <https://info.orcid.org/mapping-the-pid-landscape/>

1. Process: high-level, generic stages in the workflow
2. Activity: specific tasks undertaken as part of the process stage
3. Relevant persistent identifiers: whilst highlighting the priority PIDs, these also note other PIDs or identifiers that can be used to streamline or otherwise facilitate the activity
4. PID interaction: the specific actions taken with each PID during the task to create benefits or improvements

Stages that usually take place early in the research lifecycle are placed higher up in the diagram (although as noted above this sequencing is imperfect and these diagrams should not be seen as suggesting that the sequence portrayed is either universal or 'best').

Validation

After developing each draft diagram, a mix of follow-up validation activities were undertaken, determined largely by the availability of participants. Where a workshop could be organised in a timely way, group discussions were generally preferred, but where that proved too challenging or where a specific expert was not available, we organised multiple one-on-one calls instead. The funding workflow validation was almost entirely carried out via individual calls after the original workshop, whereas the research data workflow was completed in a series of four workshops.

After every workshop or feedback call, suggested additions and clarifications were incorporated into the workflow diagram before the next round of feedback.

Implications of the 'ideal world vision' for present day PID implementers

The vision presented in the workflow diagrams of an 'ideal world' PID-optimised future provides us with one possible destination for the current UK PID roadmap programme. In this future, DOIs, ORCIDs, RAIDs, and RORs are consistently and comprehensively used to gather and exchange information about articles, data, grants, people, projects, and organisations. Working backwards from this 'ideal world' to the real world of current practices, it is possible to plot a route to this state.

Here, we make some core recommendations that various stakeholder groups could take now to begin to lay the foundations of the PID-optimised future, which we hope will be useful to policy-makers, practitioners, systems providers, and their customers, and those seeking to get the best from their existing investments in PIDs.

For the full picture of what each recommendation would look like in action, please see the workflow diagrams.

Funders

We recommend that funders should:

1. Register DOIs for all awards, including PIDs for associated entities (people, projects, organisations, and so on), and commit to updating this information throughout the lifetime of the grant and up to the end of any reporting period.
2. Gather data about applicants, projects, and past activities (including outputs and grants) by ingesting PIDs and associated metadata wherever these are available, and encouraging investigators and institutions to register and share such PIDs.
3. Invest in the collection of PIDs in reporting and evaluation platforms, and work with PID organisations to improve the citation and tracking of PIDs throughout the ecosystem.

The benefits of these actions would be:

- Less manual data entry, resulting in better data quality and more time for contextual information to be provided
- Measurable reductions in bureaucratic burden on researchers and administrators
- More timely, more complete information about the outputs and outcomes resulting from funded research and a better basis for tracking future impacts

Repositories and publishers

We recommend that repositories and publishers should:

1. Collect and authenticate ORCID IDs for authors and reviewers during article submission, and pull in affiliation data etc. from the ORCID records of authors.
2. Integrate grant DOI search and lookup tools and pull funding acknowledgements and other data from the grant record into publication metadata.

3. Embed PIDs for projects, grants, organisations, contributors, and other entities into both outputs and metadata in human-readable and machine-actionable forms.
4. Register DOIs (or equivalent) PIDs for outputs, provide the most complete metadata possible for them at the time of registration, and commit to updating metadata records into the future.

The benefits of these actions would be:

- More accurate connections between the output and any associated entities, with consequent time and effort savings in review and metadata creation
- Maximised discoverability and citability of outputs, boosting the reach and impact of content, with easier tracking of references and other interactions
- Lower administrative overheads (review, handling of any charges, progress through different systems to publication, and so on) and an improved author experience

Research managers

We recommend that research managers should:

1. Support and incentivise researchers to get an ORCID ID and to keep their ORCID records complete and up-to-date.
2. Register RAIDs for projects, provide the most complete metadata possible for them at the time of registration, and commit to updating metadata records into the future.
3. Leverage PID registries and update notifications (e.g. Crossref/DataCite 'auto update' functionality, ORCID record notifications) to automate metadata re-use and reporting processes wherever possible.

The benefits of these actions would be:

- Streamlined administrative processes for project management and internal or external reporting, and improved research integrity/reproducibility
- Enhanced abilities to analyse research portfolios and better strategic decision-making
- Easier compliance with and monitoring of policy requirements

Research data specialists

We recommend that research data specialists should:

1. Register PIDs for datasets early in the research lifecycle, provide the most complete metadata possible for them at the time of registration, and commit to updating metadata records into the future.
2. Embed PIDs for associated entities (projects, people, organisations, facilities, instruments, physical samples, textual resources, etc.) into dataset metadata and make metadata as open as possible.
3. Use PIDs to track versioning and disposal/publication/access decisions.

The benefits of these actions would be:

- Enhanced reproducibility and integrity of research

- Clear pathways to tracking investments, impacts and outcomes of data-producing systems/processes
- Reduced project and data management overhead and better reporting to institutions and funders
- Improved strategic management of data assets

Conclusion

The first steps that we recommend based on the findings of our workflow development process are not particularly surprising. They line up well with the recommendations that PID enthusiasts have been offering for years. However, in tying them all together in these workflow diagrams, it is possible to see their full potential impact: a richer information landscape, with reduced administrative overhead, lower opportunity costs for research activities, and better project and portfolio management.

However, the benefits to each stakeholder group of taking these actions is just a part of the story. In mapping the connections between the four workflows set out in the diagrams, it is obvious that each benefit would be multiplied by others following suit with PID adoption and integration. For example, registering grant DOIs and publishing metadata reliably will not just benefit funders: it will enable significant gains for institutions, publishers, and researchers alike. Institutions registering RAIDs for projects will streamline project management, and also vastly improve research reporting and evaluation, and enable better impact analyses.

It is widely recognised that modern research is more global and more connected than ever before. Using PIDs early, and consistently, as a way to share and reuse information makes those connections work much harder for the benefit of the whole research ecosystem.

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